

Comparison of Isobaric Levobupivacaine 0.5% with Isobaric Ropivacaine 0.5% in Spinal Anaesthesia in Lower Limb Surgeries in Adult PatientsPraveen Kumar V.¹, Sharmila Narayana², Priya³, Priti Jadeja⁴, Suresh C.⁵^{1,2,3}Assistant Professor, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Institute, T Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural.⁴Professor, Shri M.P. Shah Medical College, Jamnagar.⁵Professor & HOD, Sri Siddhartha Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Institute, T Begur, Nelamangala, Bengaluru Rural

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Abstract:**Background:** Ropivacaine and Levobupivacaine are amide local anesthetics with better safety profile as compared to Bupivacaine. This study was performed to compare the anesthetic efficacy and safety of two local anesthetic agents, Isobaric 0.5% Ropivacaine and Isobaric 0.5% Levobupivacaine, in patients undergoing elective lower limb surgeries under spinal anesthesia, using 3ml (15mg) of each.**Materials and Methods:** 60 healthy consenting patients meeting our inclusion criteria were selected for the trial and randomly allotted into one of two groups of 30 each to receive intrathecally isobaric 0.5% Ropivacaine or isobaric 0.5% Levobupivacaine respectively. Characteristics of sensory and motor nerve block, intra-operative haemodynamic changes and adverse effects such as hypotension, bradycardia, vomiting, shivering were evaluated. The demographic quantitative data was analyzed by student's t' test and qualitative data was analyzed by Chi-square test using MEDCALC software.**Results:** Isobaric Levobupivacaine had a significantly similar onset and progression of sensory block and height of sensory blockade after 20min as compared to the isobaric Ropivacaine group. The onset and progression of motor block (modified Bromage scale) were similar in both groups. The duration of sensory and motor block was significantly shorter ($P < 0.01$) in Ropivacaine group (45 ± 5.14 minutes and 139 ± 10.37 minutes) as compared to the Levobupivacaine group (58 ± 9.15 minutes and 172 ± 14.4 minutes).**Conclusions:** 0.5% isobaric Ropivacaine has shorter duration and similar onset and progression of motor and sensory blockade on comparing with 0.5% isobaric Levobupivacaine intrathecally with comparable haemodynamic changes and complications.**Keywords:** Spinal anesthesia, Levobupivacaine, Ropivacaine.

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Introduction

Spinal anesthesia is obtained by blocking the spinal nerves in subarachnoid space. This provides excellent anesthesia and relaxation for lower abdominal, gynecological, perineal and lower limb surgeries. Spinal anesthesia provides faster onset and effective sensory and motor blockade [1].

New long acting local anesthetics, pure S-enantiomers of bupivacaine (ropivacaine and levobupivacaine) have recently been introduced for clinical use. The claimed benefits of these are reduced cardiac toxicity on overdose and more specific effects on sensory rather than motor nerve fibers [2]. Since only few reports are available on their intrathecal use in lower limb surgeries, this study was undertaken.

Materials and Methods

After taking permission from institutional ethical committee, a randomized double blind study was conducted. Sixty patients of ASA physical status I & II posted for elective orthopedic lower limb surgical procedure was randomly selected and divided into two groups.

First is Levobupivacaine group (group 'L'), in this isobaric Inj. Levobupivacaine 0.5% (15mg) was given for subarachnoid block and other is ROPIVACAINE group (group 'R') for this isobaric inj. Ropivacaine 0.5% (15mg) was given for subarachnoid block.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients of American Society of Anesthesiologists grade 1 and 2, Age between 18-60 years, body weight between 50-90 kgs

Exclusion Criteria: H/o skin diseases, deformities of spine, h/o coagulation disorders, any cardiovascular disease, respiratory disease, metabolic disease and central nervous system diseases, h/o adverse drug reactions, pregnant patients, patient refusal.

All patients were assessed a day before surgery and screened for any associated medical illness, any eventful previous anesthesia exposure, drug allergy, family history, postoperative anesthetic complications etc. routine investigations like hemoglobin estimation, blood sugar, serum creatinine estimation, chest x-ray and electrocardiogram were carried out to find out that all the above were within normal limits. Patients were also assessed for vitals like temperature, pulse, blood pressure and respiratory rate. Respiratory system and cardiovascular system were examined. Airway assessment was done. Spine examination was done for skin changes, edema, injuries, surgical scars, deformities, mass/cysts and interspace.

All patients were informed about the benefits and adverse reactions of drugs under study and then a written informed consent were taken and surgery was carried out on all the patients as per hospital protocol. On the day of operation, suitable IV line was secured with 18 G or 20G intravenous cannula and inj. Ringer's Lactate (500ml) started. Patients were premedicated with inj. Glycopyrrolate 4 μ g/kg IV (antisialogogue) and inj. Midazolam 0.02mg/kg i.v. (for amnesia and to relieve anxiety) 15 min before induction.

Subarachnoid block was performed with patient in lateral position. Under strict aseptic and antiseptic precautions, lumbar Puncture was performed with 23 gauge Quincke needle, at L3-L4 intervertebral space using midline approach. Following free flow of CSF, drug [Isobaric Levobupivacaine 0.5% (15mg) OR Isobaric Ropivacaine 0.5% (15mg)] was injected. The following parameters were observed and recorded:

Sensory Block: The level of sensory block was evaluated by loss of pinprick sensation by Hollmen scale [3]:

0 = ability to appreciate a pinprick as sharp.

1 = ability to appreciate a pinprick as less sharp.

2 = inability to appreciate a pin prick as sharp (analgesia).

3 = inability to appreciate a pin touching (anaesthesia).

Sensory Characteristics:

1. Onset of sensory block at shin of tibia

2. Sensory block at L1 level

3. Sensory block at T10 level

4. Final sensory level achieved in 20mins

5. Two segment regression time

Motor Block:

The motor blockade was assessed using Modified Bromage scale [4]:

0=Free movement of legs, feet, with ability to raise extended legs.

1=Inability to raise extended leg and hip flexion is decreased but full flexion to feet and knee present.

2=Inability to raise leg or flex knees, flexion of ankle and feet present.

3=Inability to raise legs, flex knees ankle or move toes.

Motor Characteristics:

1. Onset of motor block (Modified Bromage scale 1).

2. Partial motor block (Modified Bromage scale 2).

3. Complete motor block (Modified Bromage scale 3).

4. Total duration of motor block (after attaining Modified Bromage scale 0).

Monitoring:

Throughout surgery, patients were monitored for temperature, pulse, respiratory rate, BP, SPO₂, RS, CVS, ECG, Urine output and any complications like bradycardia, nausea, vomiting, headache, dizziness, hypotension, chest pain, convulsions, breathlessness and shivering.

Statistical Analysis: The demographic quantitative data was analyzed by student's t' test and qualitative data was analyzed by Chi-square test using MEDCALC software.

Observations & Results

1. Demographic Profile

There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups with regard to age, weight after applying 't' test ($p > 0.05$) and gender after applying chi-square {x²} test ($p > 0.05$, table 1, figures 1,2).

2. Sensory Block

The mean time for onset of sensory block in group L was 205 \pm 83.59 seconds and 193 \pm 82.42 seconds in group R.

The onset of sensory block in group L was delayed by only few seconds than group R ($p > 0.05$), so the difference was statistically insignificant.

The mean time for progression of sensory block to L1 in group L was 373 ± 104.33 seconds and 336 ± 98.12 seconds in group R. The progression of sensory block to L1 in group L was delayed by more seconds than group R ($p > 0.05$), but the difference was statistically insignificant.

The mean time for progression of sensory block to T10 in group L was 579 ± 150.49 seconds and 513 ± 116.9 seconds in group R. The progression of sensory block to T10 in group L was delayed by more seconds than group R ($p > 0.05$), but the difference was statistically insignificant.

On analyzing the above data, onset (shin of tibia) & progression of sensory block to L1 and T10 (assessed by loss of pinprick sensation, Hollmen scale 3[3]) was slower in group L compared to group R clinically but the difference was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$, table 2, figure 3).

With regard to the highest sensory level attained at 20mins after induction, in group L, 13.3 % achieved T4 level, followed by 33.3% achieved T6 level, 33.3 % achieved T8 level and 20% achieved T10 level.

Whereas 10 % of group R achieved T4 level, followed by 36.7% achieved T6 level, 46.7 % achieved T8 level and 6.7% achieved T10 level.

This implied group L achieved highest sensory level block(T4) at 20mins more than group R even though T6 and T8 levels were achieved more by group R than group L but the difference was statistically insignificant after applying chi-square $\{\chi^2\}$ test ($p > 0.05$, table 3, figure 4).

3. Motor Block

The mean time for onset of motor block in group L was 220 ± 104.71 seconds and 202 ± 83.19 seconds in group R. The onset of motor block in group L was delayed by only few seconds than group R ($p > 0.05$), so the difference was statistically insignificant.

The mean time for progression to partial motor block in group L was 374 ± 133.44 seconds and 374 ± 95.20 seconds in group R. The progression to partial motor block in group L was almost same as in group R ($p > 0.05$), so the difference was statistically insignificant.

The mean time for progression to complete motor block in group L was 555 ± 181.53 seconds and 549 ± 111.43 seconds in group R. The progression to complete motor block in group L was delayed only by few seconds than group R ($p > 0.05$), so the difference was statistically insignificant.

On analyzing the above data, onset of motor block, partial and complete motor block (assessed by

modified bromage scale[4]) was slower in group L compared to group R clinically but the difference was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$, table 4, figure 5).

4. Recovery of Blockade:

The time for 2 segment regression of sensory block was considerably slower in Group L, 58 ± 9.15 minutes when compared to Group R which was 45 ± 5.14 minutes. This difference was statistically highly significant ($p < 0.01$).

The mean total duration of motor block was considerably longer in Group L, 172 ± 14.4 minutes when compared to Group R which was 139 ± 10.37 minutes. This difference was statistically highly significant ($p < 0.01$).

On analyzing the above data, recovery from sensory and motor block was considerably longer in group L than group R, as the difference was statistically highly significant ($p < 0.01$, table 5, figure 6).

5. Pulse Rate

Statistically significant difference in mean pulse rate between group L and group R was seen only at 120mins ($p < 0.05$, table 6, figure 7) after induction but was clinically not significant as mean values do not fall under bradycardia ($< 60/\text{min}$) or tachycardia ($> 100/\text{min}$) for the given age and clinical picture.

6. Mean Arterial Blood Pressure

Statistically significant difference in MAP (mmHg) between group L and group R was seen only at 30mins ($p < 0.01$) and significant difference at 45mins ($p < 0.05$) after induction but was clinically not significant (table 7, figure 8) as mean values do not vary beyond 20% of mean arterial blood pressure for the given age and clinical picture.

7. Respiratory Rate

Statistically significant difference in mean respiratory rate between group L and group R was seen at 1min ($p < 0.05$, table 8, figure 9) and highly significant difference at 10mins ($p < 0.01$) after induction but was clinically not significant as mean values do not fall under bradypnoea ($< 12/\text{min}$) or tachypnoea ($> 20/\text{min}$) for the given age and clinical picture.

8. Intraoperative Complications

On applying chi-square $\{\chi^2\}$ test, there was statistically insignificant difference ($p > 0.05$) on incidence of bradycardia, hypotension, nausea, vomiting and shivering between both groups. Other side effects like chest pain, convulsions and breathlessness were not seen in either group (Table 9, figure 10).

Table 1: Demographic Profile

Parameter	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Male	26 (86.67%)*	23 (76.67%)*	0.98	NS
Female	4 (13.33%)*	7 (23.33%)*	0.96	NS
AGE(YEARS)	30.4±10.00	32.1±10.5	0.52	NS
WEIGHT(Kg)	63.83±6.65	65.5±6.61	0.33	NS

*Values are expressed as n (%), Values are expressed as mean + SD, NS-Not significant

Table 2: Comparison of Onset and Progression of Sensory Block

Time Required (Secs)				
Sensory Block	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Onset(shin of tibia)	205±83.59	193±82.42	0.58	NS
L1 reached in	373±104.33	336±98.12	0.16	NS
T10 reached in	579±150.49	513±116.9	0.06	NS

Values are expressed as mean + SD, NS-Not significant

Table 3: Comparison of Height of Sensory Blockade

Height Of Sensory Block In 20 Mins	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	P Value	Significance
T4	4(13.3%)*	3(10%)*	1.00	NS
T6	10(33.3%)*	11(36.7%)*	1.00	NS
T8	10(33.3%)*	14(46.7%)*	0.43	NS
T10	6(20%)*	2(6.7%)*	0.26	NS

Values are expressed as n (%), NS-Not significant

Table 4: Comparison of Onset and Progression of Motor Block

Time Required (Secs)				
Motor Block	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Onset(Modified Bromage 1)	220±104.71	202±83.19	0.46	NS
Partial(Modified Bromage 2)	374±133.44	374±95.20	1.00	NS
Complete(Modified Bromage 3)	555±181.53	549±111.43	0.88	NS

Values are expressed as mean + SD, NS-Not significant

Table 5: Comparison of Recovery Parameters

Time Required (Mins)				
Recovery	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Sensory-Two segment regression	58±9.15	45±5.14	<0.0001	HS
Motor-Total duration of block	172±14.40	139±10.37	<0.0001	HS

Values are expressed as mean + SD, HS-Highly significant

Table 6: Comparison of Mean Pulse Rate

Pulse Rate				
Time (Mins)	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Before Premedication	84.9±9.15	85±9.8	0.97	NS
Before Induction	85.4±9.38	86±10	0.81	NS
After Induction				
1 MIN	89±11	88±11	0.72	NS
5 MINS	90.1±12.1	89±12	0.72	NS
10 MINS	91±13	90±11	0.75	NS
20 MINS	92±16	90±13	0.60	NS
30 MINS	91±18	91±14	1.00	NS
45 MINS	89±15	90±13	0.78	NS
60 MINS	88.4±16.2	89±12	0.87	NS
75 MINS	87.7±15	87±9.2	0.83	NS
90 MINS	90±11	88±8.2	0.43	NS
120 MINS	90±8	86±6	0.03	S

Values are expressed as mean + SD, S-significant, NS-Not significant, HS-Highly significant

Table 7: Comparison of Mean Arterial Pressure

Mean Arterial Pressure (mmHg)				
Time (Mins)	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Before Premedication	94.58±4.38	93.16±3.14	0.15	NS
Before Induction	94.1±3.89	93±2.86	0.22	NS
After Induction				
1 Min	92.4±3.65	92±2.8	0.64	NS
5 Mins	90±4.1	90±3.5	1.00	NS
10 Mins	88±5	88±4.5	1.00	NS
20 Mins	87.3±5.28	86±4.4	0.31	NS
30 Mins	88±5.2	84±5.8	0.007	HS
45 Mins	88.9±4.35	86±5.7	0.03	S
60 Mins	90±4.7	88±4.7	0.10	NS
75 Mins	89.8±3.79	89±3.9	0.42	NS
90 Mins	90.3±3.01	89±4.1	0.17	NS
120 Mins	91±3.1	89±5	0.07	NS

Values are expressed as mean + SD, S-significant, NS-Not significant, HS-Highly significant

Table 8: Comparison of Mean Respiratory Rate

Respiratory Rate				
Time (Mins)	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Before Premedication	15.7±1.06	16±1.1	0.29	NS
Before Induction	15.6±0.97	16±1	0.12	NS
After Induction				
1 MIN	15.5±1.01	16±0.9	0.048	S
5 MINS	16±1	16±0.8	1.00	NS
10 MINS	15±1.1	16±1	0.001	HS
20 MINS	16±1.1	16±0.9	1.00	NS
30 MINS	16±1	16±1	1.00	NS
45 MINS	16±1.1	16±1.1	1.00	NS
60 MINS	16±1	16±1	1.00	NS
75 MINS	16±1.1	16±1	1.00	NS
90 MINS	15.6±1.09	16±0.7	0.10	NS
120 MINS	16±0.7	16±1.1	1.00	NS

Values are expressed as mean + SD, S-significant, NS-Not significant, HS-Highly significant

Table 9: Comparison of Intra-Operative Complications

Complications	Group 'L'	Group 'R'	'P' Value	Significance
Bradycardia	1(3.3%)	0(0%)	1.00	NS
Hypotension	3(10%)	4(13.3%)	1.00	NS
Nausea	2(6.7%)	3(10%)	1.00	NS
Vomiting	0(0%)	1(3.3%)	1.00	NS
Chest Pain	0(0%)	0(0%)	-	-
Convulsions	0(0%)	0(0%)	-	-
Shivering	1(3.3%)	1(3.3%)	0.47	NS
Breathlessness	0(0%)	0(0%)	-	-

Values are expressed as n (%). S-significant, NS-Not significant, HS-Highly significant

Figure 1: Sex Ratio

Figure 2: Comparison of Mean Age and Weight

Figure 3: Comparison of Onset and Progression of Sensory Block

Figure 4: Comparison of Maximum Height of Sensory Block

Figure 5: Comparison of Onset and Progression of Motor Block

Figure 6: Comparison of Recovery of Sensory and Motor Blockade

Figure 7: Comparison of Mean Pulse Rate

Figure 8: Comparison of Mean Arterial Pressure

Figure 9: Comparison of Mean Respiratory Rate

Figure 10: Comparison of Intraoperative Complications

Discussion

Spinal anesthesia consists of the temporary interruption of nerve transmission within the subarachnoid space produced by injection of a local anesthetic solution into cerebrospinal fluid [1]. Spinal anesthesia with hyperbaric bupivacaine 0.5% is a popular method.

New long-acting local anesthetics, pure S-enantiomers of bupivacaine (ropivacaine and levobupivacaine in 1990s) have recently been introduced for clinical use. The claimed benefits of these are reduced cardiac toxicity on overdose and more specific effects on sensory rather than motor nerve fibers [2].

Levobupivacaine is an amino amide local anesthetic drug and a pure S-enantiomer of bupivacaine. It is a long acting local anaesthetic

and analgesic. It reversibly blocks nerve conduction in sensory and motor nerves [5].

Ropivacaine is a new amino amide long acting local anaesthetic. It is having a propyl group on the piperidine nitrogen atom of the molecule in contrast to bupivacaine which contains butyl group [6]. It is less lipophilic than bupivacaine and is less likely to penetrate large myelinated motor fibers; therefore, it has selective action on the pain-transmitting A δ and C nerves rather than A α fibres, which are involved in motor function [7].

The aim of this study was to compare isobaric Levobupivacaine 0.5% and isobaric Ropivacaine 0.5% for spinal anaesthesia. Our study design consisted of 60 patients aged between 18 – 60 years, ASA physical status I or II, body weight 50-90 kgs undergoing elective lower limb surgeries of duration of maximum 120 minutes under spinal anesthesia who were randomly divided into two

groups. Group L (Levobupivacaine group) patients received 0.5% isobaric levobupivacaine 15 mg (3 ml) and Group R (Ropivacaine group) received 0.5% isobaric ropivacaine 15 mg (3 ml) intrathecally.

Demographic Profile across the Group

In our study, majority of patients were middle aged in both the groups. In group L there were 26 males and 4 females. In group R there were 23 males and 7 females. The mean age and weight in either group were also identical.

The mean age of patients in group L was 30.4 ± 10.00 years compared to 32.1 ± 10.5 years in group R. The mean weight of the patients in group L was 63.83 ± 6.65 kgs and in group R was 65.5 ± 6.61 kgs.

There was no statistically significant difference between the two groups with regard to age, weight and gender (table 1).

Sensory and Motor Blockade:

1. Onset and Progression of Sensory Blockade (Hollmen Scale 3)

In our study, onset of sensory block in group L was delayed by only few seconds than group R but the difference was statistically insignificant. The progression of sensory block to L1 in group L was delayed by more seconds than group R but the difference was statistically insignificant. The progression of sensory block to T10 in group L was delayed by more seconds than group R but the difference was statistically insignificant (table 2).

These results are comparable to other studies:

Gautier P [8] et al in 2003 studied the comparison of the effects of intrathecal ropivacaine, levobupivacaine, and bupivacaine for Caesarean section. They concluded that mean onset time of sensory blockade at T10 dermatome did not differ significantly between levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups. Breebaart MB [9] et al in 2003 evaluated urinary bladder scanning after day-case arthroscopy under spinal anaesthesia and compared between lidocaine, ropivacaine, and levobupivacaine. They found that levobupivacaine and ropivacaine did not differ significantly in mean onset and progression of sensory block and was slower than lidocaine.

2. Maximum Height of Sensory Blockade after 20mins of Induction

In our study, group L achieved highest sensory level block (T4) at 20mins more than group R even though T6 and T8 levels were achieved more by group R than group L but the difference was statistically insignificant (table 3).

These results are comparable to other studies:

R. Parpaglioni [10] et al in 2006 evaluated minimum local anaesthetic dose (MLAD) of intrathecal levobupivacaine and ropivacaine for Caesarean section. They found that maximum height of sensory blockade did not differ significantly among levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups.

Kim KM [11] et al in 2013 compared clinically relevant doses of intrathecal ropivacaine and levobupivacaine with fentanyl for labor analgesia. They found that maximum height of sensory blockade did not differ significantly among levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups.

3. Onset and Progression of Motor Blockade (Modified Bromage Scale)

In our study, onset of motor block in group L was delayed by only few seconds than group R, so the difference was statistically insignificant. The progression to partial motor block in group L was almost same as in group R, so the difference was statistically insignificant. The progression to complete motor block in group L was delayed only by few seconds than group R, so the difference was statistically insignificant (table 4).

These results are comparable to other studies:

Casati A [12] et al in 2004 compared unilateral spinal anesthesia with hyperbaric bupivacaine, ropivacaine and levobupivacaine for inguinal herniorrhaphy. They concluded that mean onset time of motor blockade and complete motor block did not differ significantly between levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups.

Ashton Dionel D'Souza [13] et al in 2014 compared intrathecal hyperbaric 0.5% bupivacaine, isobaric 0.5% levobupivacaine and isobaric 0.75% ropivacaine for lower abdominal surgeries. They concluded that median onset time of motor blockade and complete motor block did not differ significantly between levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups.

4. Recovery Parameters

In our study, the time for 2 segment regression of sensory block was considerably slower in Group L when compared to Group R. This difference was statistically highly significant. The mean total duration of motor block was considerably longer in Group L when compared to Group R. This difference was statistically highly significant (table 5).

These results are comparable to other studies:

Cappelleri G [14] et al in 2005 evaluated spinal anesthesia with hyperbaric levobupivacaine and ropivacaine for outpatient knee arthroscopy. They found that levobupivacaine had longer sensory and motor blockade than ropivacaine. A Mehta [15] et

al in 2007 evaluated intrathecal administration of newer local anaesthetic agent's ropivacaine and levobupivacaine with bupivacaine in patients undergoing lower limb surgery.

They found that levobupivacaine had longer sensory and motor blockade than ropivacaine attributable to a greater intrinsic vasoconstrictor property of levobupivacaine.

Vital Parameters

1. Pulse Rate

In our study on the mean pulse rate in group L and group R was clinically not significant as mean values do not fall under bradycardia (<60/min) or tachycardia (>100/min) for the given age and clinical picture (table 6).

2. Blood Pressure

Mean Arterial Pressure

In our study on MAP (mmHg) in group L and group R was clinically not significant (table 14) as mean values do not vary beyond 20% of mean arterial blood pressure for the given age and clinical picture (table 7).

3. Respiratory Rate

In our study on mean respiratory rate in group L and group R was clinically not significant as mean values do not fall under bradypnea (<12/min) or tachypnoea (>20/min) for the given age and clinical picture (table 8).

These results are comparable to other studies:

A Mehta [15] et al in 2007 evaluated intrathecal administration of newer local anaesthetic agent's ropivacaine and levobupivacaine with bupivacaine in patients undergoing lower limb surgery. They concluded that there was no significant change in intra-operative vital parameters between levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups.

Mantouvalou M [16] et al in 2008 compared plain ropivacaine, bupivacaine and levobupivacaine intrathecally for lower abdominal surgery. They concluded that there was no significant change in intra-operative vital parameters between levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups. Ashton Dionel D'Souza [13] et al in 2014 compared intrathecal hyperbaric 0.5% bupivacaine, isobaric 0.5% levobupivacaine and isobaric 0.75% ropivacaine for lower abdominal surgeries. They concluded that there were no significant changes in intra-operative vital parameters between levobupivacaine and ropivacaine groups.

Complications

In our study, in group L, 3.3% patients experienced bradycardia, 6.7% experienced nausea, 10% experienced hypotension and 3.3% experienced

shivering. Whereas in group R, 13.3% patients experienced hypotension, 10% experienced nausea, 3.3% experienced vomiting and 3.3% experienced shivering. There was statistically insignificant difference on incidence of bradycardia, hypotension, and nausea, vomiting and shivering between both groups (table 9)

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